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Research Article

**SURGICALLY TREATED EARLY STAGE CERVICAL
CANCER –ADJUVANT TREATMENT AND PROGNOSTIC
FACTORS**¹Dr Ayesha Zafar, ²Dr Shahwaza Ajmal, ³Dr Anam Nazir¹Avicenna Medical College, Lahore²Avicenna Medical College, Lahore³Fatima Jinnah Medical University, Lahore**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:**

Invasive cervical cancer is considered a preventable disease because it has a long pre-invasive condition. If it is detected in the early stages, that is, up to stage IIA1, the disease can be treated with a good survival rate.

Aim: *To identify the prognostic factors in surgically treated early stage cervical cancer. To study if preoperative findings could accurately predict presence of poor prognostic factors such as nodal Status. To evaluate these histological prognostic factors in deciding the further management of patient with adjuvant treatment.*

Place and Duration: *In the Obstetric and Gynecology department Unit-II of Nishtar Hospital Multan for one-year duration from May 2019 to May 2020.*

Methods: *This is a prospective study of prognostic factors and complementary treatment in 60 cases of early cervical cancer, which are treated surgically to assess histological prognostic factors and decide on the next treatment of the adjuvant patient (radical hysterectomy with pelvic node sediment). Histopathological results were evaluated to determine the prognosis.*

Results: *Involvement of lymph nodes in 25% of cases and invasion of lymph space was observed in 15%. Parametrium was 16.6%. There were 3 patients with a positive margin and 65% of patients had moderate tumor differentiation. The maximum number of nodes in stage IB2 was positive. The size of the tumor larger than 4 cm is an important determinant of the prognosis and has a definite effect on the metastasis to the lymph nodes and other missing factors of histological prognosis.*

Conclusion: *Adjuvant therapy applies to patients with moderate to high prognosis*

Keywords: *cervical cancer, surgical treatment, risk factors.*

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INTRODUCTION:

Cervical cancer is fatal, but preventable and curable diseases can be. If it is detected on time, that is, to the IIA scenario, it can be supported. However, recurrent complementary therapy in the form of radiation therapy is necessary to prevent treatment. Radiation therapy itself, a. diarrhea b. Abdominal cramps c. Frequent urination e. Bleeding from the bladder and intestinal mucosa and chronic complications such as a. Proctosigmoiditis have their own morbidity over a period of time. To avoid these diseases, we need to rationalize which patients really need complementary treatment and can only be monitored without adjuvant treatment. The purpose of this study is to analyses predictive factors in which complementary treatments can be decided and rationalized.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was held in the Obstetrics and Gynecology department Unit-II of Nishtar Hospital Multan for one-year duration from May 2019 to May 2020. This is a prospective study of prognostic factors and complementary treatment in 60 early stages of cervical cancer, which was surgically treated during the cervical cancer phase operated.

- Operated cases of early stage cervical cancer FIGO stage IB to stage IIA1

Exclusion criteria:

- FIGO stage IA and Advanced cervical cancer from IIA2/ IIB to stage IV

- Medically inadequate patients with early cervical cancer are not treated surgically.

Histo-pathological findings were evaluated to determine the prognosis. Adjuvant treatment was individualized based on the histo-pathological prognostic factors Type of adjuvant treatment included radiotherapy, chemotherapy and concurrent chemo-radiation.

Adjuvant pelvic radiation was given in two circumstances:

I. Patients with positive nodes, parametria, or surgical margins

II. Patients with negative nodes but high-risk features in the primary tumor

Prognostic factors include

- Primary tumor size
 - Depth of the stromal invasion
 - Lymph-vascular space invasion
- High-risk histological factors
- Condition of lymph nodes.
 - Parametrial extension
 - Status of the vaginal margins

Patients with intermediate risk were given radiation therapy alone, however patients with high risk factors were given concurrent chemoradiation. These patients were followed at 3month interval after completion of treatment. Recurrence over a period of minimum 6 months to 2 years post operatively was studied.

RESULTS:

Table: 1. Number of patients in each stage of disease.

Stage	n = 60	Percentage
IB1	29	48.3%
IB2	26	43.3%
IIA1	5	8.3%

Table: 2. Overall histologic prognostic factors analysed

Histological prognostic factors	Present study	
	N = 60	%
Tumour cell type		
Squamous cell carcinoma	52	86.7
Adenocarcinoma	6	10
Others	2	3.3
Depth of stromal invasion		
< 2/3 rd invasion	37	61.6
>2/3 rd invasion	23	38.3
Lymphovascularspace invasion		
Present	9	15
Absent	51	85
Parametrial involvement		
Present	10	16.6

Absent	50	83.4
Lymph node involvement		
Present	15	25
Absent	45	75
Differentiaton		
Well	2	3.3
Moderate	39	65
Poor	19	31.6
Margins		
Positive	3	5
Negative	57	95

Table: 3. Stage and lymph node involvement

Stage	n=60	Present study	
		Lymph node positive n=15	%
IB1	N=29	6	20.6
IB2	N=26	8	30.7
IIA ₁	N=5	1	20

Table: 4. Size of tumor and lymphnode involvement

Size of tumor	Lymph node involved (%)
< 4 cm	20
> 4 cm	32

Table:5. Depth of stromal invasion and lymph node involvement

Depth of invasion	Lymph node positive (%)
<2/3 rd	13.51
>2/3 rd	43.47

Table:6. Lymphovascular space invasion and lymph node metastasis.

LVSI	Lymph node positive (%)
Present	55.5
Absent	19.6

Table:7. Stage and number of associated risk factors

Stage	High risk	Intermediate risk	Low ris k	Intermediate risk + high risk
IB ₁	3.4	51.7	20.6	24.1
IB ₂	3.8	42.3	3.8	50
IIA1		40		60

Table: 8. Adjuvant treatment

Adjuvant treatment		Percentage of patients
RT		53.3
CT-RT		23.3
Observation		15
Lost to follow up	Adjuvant treatment not taken	6.6
	Incomplete adjuvant treatment	1.6

Table :9 Stage and adjuvant treatment

Stage	RT %	CT-RT %	Observation %	Lost to follow up%
IB ₁	51.7	17.2	24.1	6.8
IB ₂	65.3	23	7.6	3.8
IIA ₁		80		20

Table: 10 Follow up

Follow up	Duration - one year
Free of disease n=52	86.6%
Alive of disease n=8	13.3%

Table: 11 Recurrence in relation to treatment

Recurrence	Total Number n=8	Over all Percentage 13.33%
After treatment	3	5%
Lost to follow up/incomplete treatment	5	8.33%

Table:12 High risk factors in recurrence after completing adjuvant treatment

Recurrence	High risk factors	Intermediate risk factors
Recurrence 1	Lymph node involved	>½ stromal thickness ,moderate differentiation, uterus involved
Recurrence 2	Lymph node involved	>½ stromal thickness, moderate differentiation
Recurrence 3	Lymph node involved	>½ stromal thickness, poor differentiation

DISCUSSION:

Cervical cancer is a clinically staged cancer. Ca cervix is considered able to work according to studies up to stage IIA1. The preferred treatment for IIA1 is primary radiation therapy. However, all surgical cases should be carefully evaluated to prevent recurrence and ensure the patient's disease-free survival. Presence of high risk of histological prognostic factors for recurrence in tumor a) Positive or close margins b) Positive lymph nodes (c) Microscopic parametric involvement. Otherwise, (a) Large tumor size b) Medium or deep chipping infestation 1/3a c) Moderate risk factors such as lymphatic vascular space invasion make the patient the right candidate for adjuvant therapy (5). In this study, we will examine these factors to rationalize the need for complementary treatment and thus prevent the long-term morbidity of these treatments. This study shows that the size of the tumor plays an important role in deciding on the

prognosis. The stage where the tumor size is more than 4 cm is associated with poor IB2 prognosis factors, and all these patients, including IIA1, were treated with a combination of chemotherapy and radiotherapy instead of radiotherapy itself. The limitation of these tests is the sample size and a short circuit of the observation period (1 year). Relapses were observed in 8 patients who completed the procedure in 3 patients and 5 patients were found guilty. These 3 patients identified high risk factors. This study observed that low-risk patients can be safely observed without adjuvant therapy, thereby preventing disease.

CONCLUSION:

Therefore, we come to the conclusion that the size of the tumor larger than 4 cm is an important determinant of the prognosis and has a definite effect on the metastasis to the lymph nodes and

other factors of poor histological prognosis. Adjuvant therapy applies to patients with moderate to high prognosis. In those high-risk patients who do not receive adjuvant therapy, relapses often. In such cases, adjuvant therapy is necessary. However, patients with indirect risk factors also require adjuvant therapy. Only low-risk cases can be stored for observation with successful results.

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